

World Biodiversity Forum – Final Resolution

Davos, Switzerland, February 28, 2020

Adopted by acclamation by the participants of the inaugural World Biodiversity Forum.

Distributed to participants and interested parties for redistribution.

The inaugural World Biodiversity Forum (<https://www.worldbiodiversityforum.org/>) was organised by bioDISCOVERY (<https://biodiscovery.earth/>), a Global Research Project (GRP) of FutureEarth (<https://futureearth.org/>), fostering collaborative interdisciplinary activities on biodiversity and ecosystem science, the University of Zurich (<https://www.uzh.ch/>) and its Research Priority Programme on “Global Change and Biodiversity” (<https://www.gcb.uzh.ch/>).

Recommendations adopted by acclamation by the participants

The World Biodiversity Forum, held from February 23–28, 2020 in Davos, Switzerland, on the occasion of the celebration of its inaugural meeting.

Considering the unique, broad, and interdisciplinary work accomplished by the Forum and the effectiveness of its working methods,

Confirming that the Forum’s mission is to advance biodiversity research in an integrative, interdisciplinary, and transparent fashion, and advance transdisciplinary approaches in biodiversity,

Confirming that the Forum’s aim is to support and accelerate transformative approaches ranging from fundamental research to implementation,

Recognizing that the Forum’s mission is to facilitate interactions between all stakeholders relevant to biodiversity, including private, corporate, governmental, non-governmental, non-profit, academic, educators and other parties acting within and across national and international borders,

Recognizing that the Forum is developing into a global centre servicing the advancement of biodiversity competences with all involved parties,

Considering that it is essential that the Forum continues to be effectively and interactively supported by key stakeholders, philanthropies, and international organisations,

Congratulates the Forum organizers on its contributions to advancing integrative and interdisciplinary biodiversity research and its implementation,

Urges involved parties both to maintain and enhance their support for the Forum and to encourage parties who are not yet involved to join the Forum,

Recommends to all relevant parties that they

1. Continue to *facilitate highly interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary research*, transgressing boundaries by implementing a rigorous OpenScience based approach to holistically address all facets of biodiversity,
2. *Value research contributions from all sources*, taking into account – but independent of – conventional impact metrics,
3. *Integrate biodiversity in all assessments, policy decisions and actions* affecting human well-being, ensuring a broader dissemination of understanding and valuing nature and its benefits to people, including a more responsible attitude of humans towards the health of the rest of the living world,
4. Ensure that the *targets in the post-2020 framework balance the need for clarity and brevity with the need to recognise the complexity of nature and its contributions to people*,
5. Develop an *integrated biodiversity monitoring system* that harnesses available and emerging remote sensing data from the world's space agencies, integrated with in-situ observations and predictive modelling to inform option assessment and to evaluate the effectiveness of international agreements and policies,
6. *Integrate biodiversity solutions across spatial and temporal scales* with climate change interventions to ensure synergies between interventions addressing climate and biodiversity change,
7. Work towards *integrating ecological integrity* (i.e., maintaining and restoring natural processes) into biodiversity targets in a changing future to allow for upgrading and upscaling of functional areas for biodiversity over space and time,
8. Create a mechanism to consider and *include the aspirations and needs of the youth*, and everyone who identifies with them,
9. Commit resources in support of the *involvement of early career researchers* on biodiversity from the low income/lower income countries,
10. Work towards *broadening our understanding of the diverse knowledge systems* and values related to and about biodiversity, ecosystem processes and their fundamental role for human systems, and creation of an egalitarian and integrated knowledge environment,
11. Commit resources to substantially *expand the capacity of biodiversity research and innovation*, in particular by inclusion of indigenous values and rights knowledge,
12. *Expand normative approaches in sustainable finance* so as to not subsidize environmental damage, and embrace a reasonable assessment of the value of life,
13. Ensure that *all Earth's biomes receive sufficient attention and consideration*,
14. Ask for *strong collaboration between the CBD and IPBES and the Forum* as a part of linking up with the science community,
15. Support, as mandated by the participants, the University of Zurich and FutureEarth Global Research Project bioDISCOVERY, to *initiate necessary steps to organize the 2nd World Biodiversity Forum*, and
16. Work in cooperation with the Forum to *develop effective mechanisms to implement these recommendations*.

In agreement with the recent findings of UN Biodiversity, CBD and IPBES we urge national governments and international organisations to act responsibly and without delay towards biodiversity by including all relevant stakeholders with the ultimate goal to safeguard all life on Earth.

World Biodiversity Forum Origin

The World Biodiversity Forum was established in 2018 by the steering committee of bioDISCOVERY and implemented by Cornelia Krug (science officer bioDISCOVERY), Bernhard Schmid and Michael Schaeppman (bioDISCOVERY steering committee members).

World Biodiversity Forum Numbers

More than 520 participants from 60 countries, ranging from the poles to the tropics, joined the World Biodiversity Forum at the Davos Congress Centre, 23 – 28 February 2020. The 5-day open science conference was composed of 62 sessions and workshops, 162 oral contributions, 5 panel discussions, 3 poster sessions, and 3 public lectures.

The Forum hosted a total of 18 plenary speakers covering a broad range of disciplines and expertise, covering biodiversity, ecosystem and earth system science; (ecological) economics; anthropology; ethics; and philosophy.

Sandra Diaz, National University of Cordoba
 Jens-Christian Svenning, Aarhus University
 Markku Oksanen, University of Eastern Finland
 Pragati Sahni, University of New Delhi
 David Tilman, University of Minnesota
 Andy Purvis, Natural History Museum London
 Unai Pascual, Basque Centre for Climate Change
 Lenore Fahrig, Carleton University
 Odette Curtis, Renosterveld Restoration Trust
 Emma Archer, University of Pretoria
 Eduardo Brondizio, Indiana University Bloomington
 Rashid Sumaila, University of British Columbia
 Barend Erasmus, University of Pretoria
 Workineh Kelbessa, Addis Ababa University
 Fabio Scarano, Federal University of Rio de Janeiro
 Benis Egoh, University of California Irvine
 Gary Varner, Texas A&M University
 Andrew Light, George Mason University and World Resources Institute

World Biodiversity Forum Sponsors

UZH University of Zurich
 MNF Faculty of Science, University of Zurich
 URPP GCB University of Zurich Research Priority Program on Global Change and Biodiversity
 GRC Graduate Research Campus, University of Zurich
 SNF Swiss National Science Foundation
 ESA European Space Agency
 NASA National Aeronautics and Space Administration
 FutureEarth Global network of scientists, researchers and innovators collaborating for a more sustainable planet
 Caran d'Ache Maison Caran D'Ache, Geneve
 WSL Swiss Federal Institute for Forest, Snow and Landscape Research
 ID-GENE DNA-based biodiversity monitoring

World Biodiversity Forum Exhibitors

nhbs wildlife, ecology, conservation
 BES British Ecological Society
 BioFID Specialised Information Service Biodiversity Research
 BiodivERsA Network of national and regional funding organisations promoting pan-European research on biodiversity and ecosystem services, and offering innovative opportunities for the conservation and sustainable management of biodiversity.